

SHORT NOTES

Isolation of Rhetsinine (Hydroxyevodiamine) in the Stem-bark of *Zanthoxylum Oxyphyllum* Edgew.

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The chloroform extract of the dried and powdered stem-bark of *Zanthoxylum oxyphyllum* Edgew., previously defatted with petroleum (60-80°), on usual processing for alkaloids furnished a yellow base. It was crystallised from benzene or ethanol in needles, m.p. 198°, which turned red on drying *in vacuo* (113-14°/5 mm). This red substance on subsequent crystallisations from benzene and ethanol regenerated the yellow base.

The alkaloid shows light absorption in the UV region: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 284, 312, and 317 m μ (log ϵ , 3.92, 4.16, and 4.17). In its IR spectrum characteristic peaks for bonded -OH (2.92 μ), for -NH (3.00 μ), and for two conjugated carbonyls (twin peaks at 5.94 and 6.00 μ) are discernible. The elemental analysis, spectral measurements, and other physical and chemical properties of this alkaloid suggested its identity with rhetsinine (I), which was first isolated by one of us¹ from *Zanthoxylum rhetsa* DC., and its structure was established as 2-hydroxyevodiamine(I) by the degradative experiments and by the synthesis from evodiamine² (IV) and also from 2-keto-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro- β -carboline and methyl *N*-methylantranilate according to the method of Patcher and Suld³.

The identity of the yellow base from *Z. oxyphyllum* with rhetsinine was subsequently confirmed by a direct comparison of their spectra, which were superimposable, and also from their X-ray diffraction patterns.

Incidentally, the red compound, obtained from rhetsinine on drying *in vacuo*, is an anhydronium base of rhetsinine, i.e., dehydroevodiamine (V), which is also a natural product, recently isolated from the leaves of *Evodia rutaecarpa* Hook. f. and Thoms. by Nakasato *et al.*⁴

According to Patcher and Suld³, rhetsinine has the structure (II) with D ring open but not closed as shown in (I). This argument was put forward to explain the twin peak in the IR spectrum of the compound, although they disregarded important chemical and other evidences¹ for structure (I), viz., (a) conversion of rhetsinine (I) to evodiamine (IV) by NaBH₄ or catalytic hydrogenation; (b) presence of -NH and -OH bands in the IR spectrum of the base; (c) transformation of rhetsinine to dehydroevodiamine having condensed ring

1. Chatterjee *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, 7, 257.
2. Chatterjee *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1960, 25, 493.
3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1680.
4. *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1962, 82, 619.

structure (V) and *vice versa*; (d) *pK* of rhetsinine, which is only 7, whereas structure (II), proposed by Patcher and Suld³, demands a higher value.

It is, however, well known⁵ that a carbinol-amine base like (I) can exist in two other tautomeric forms, viz., carbonylic (aldehydic or ketonic) (II) and ammonium (III) forms. So the statement made by Patcher and Suld³ that structure (I) for rhetsinine is wrong, is not justified. The structure (I) for rhetsinine proposed earlier⁴ is indeed correct, structure (II)² being its only tautomeric form. This has been recently confirmed by Nakasato *et al.*⁶ who have shown that both (I) and (II) represent the correct constitution of rhetsinine.

During synthesis of rhetsinine, the ammonium form (III) for this base has been recognised, which subsequently passes on to (I) the latter being in equilibrium with (II).

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5. Gadamer *et al.*, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1901, 239, 648; 1905, 243, 31.